

How to network effectively as a beginner in business?

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Abstract

Networking is essential for beginner in business, helping them develop partnerships, build valuable connections, and open up new opportunities. Networking for new business starters provides the necessary skills through data gathered through primary and secondary research. This article explores the role of social media in improving relationships, its impact on business, and effective networking strategies. It also provides information on the convenience, benefits, and opportunities of online and in-person events for new business starters and it also provides information about the role of social media in brand development. This study explains the importance of networking for personal and professional development and how to do it effectively.

Key words: Networking, Partnerships, Social media, Brand development, Relationships, Professional development.

Introduction

When starting a business, connecting with other people is a key part of the road to success. This process is called networking, and it helps find customers, partners, and people who can help you grow your business. Nowadays, social media is an integral part of our lives. It can also help you grow your business, discover new opportunities, and make new friends. For those starting a new business, platforms like Instagram and LinkedIn can help build trust and make it easier to connect with people. This article will show how important networking is for new businesses and the benefits of using it effectively.

Literature review

It is generally accepted that networks are among the most effective means of doing business, particularly for the novices. Employment (2022), as cited, defines a network as the creation of genuine contact that can result in opportunities [1]. Such links assist businesses in enhancing their capabilities , looking for partners, clients, and even secure a job. Losey (2023) contends that network creation is a long term investment and claims that for strong network, time is required to be invested [2]. Social networks like LinkedIn and Instagram are powerful instruments for business networks. Ruby (2023) claims that LinkedIn is a great way to interact with B2B and B2C markets and their partners where over a billion people are registered [3]. Just like that, social networking site Instagram (Dean, 2024) has over 2 billion users and allows businesses to promote their goods and services to a large audience, which translates into more brand and customer recall [4]. Launching on both channels provides new companies with better opportunities to reach their audience and maintain a credible online presence.

Research methodology

In this study, both primary and secondary research methods are used as well as the quantitative research approaching was used too as a survey.

Primary research

how long have you been in business?

The survey I conducted was mainly among those who had just started a business. The total number of respondents was more than 100. First of all, I asked them how long they had been in business. As you can see from the figure, 63.6% of the participants had been in business for less than 6 months. 22.7% of people had been in business for less than 12 months. The smallest proportion of participants was 13.6%, and this represents participants who had been in business for less than 3 years. From this, we can see that more than 2/3 of our participants had recently started their business.

Do you attend networking events?

Then our second question was about whether they attend or not. You can see the results, almost 70% of people attend networking events. With a little more than 30% statistics, we can see those who do not attend networking events. From this we can conclude that most of the people who have just started a business attend networking events.

How often do you attend networking events?

What is your main goal when networking for your business?

We asked about how often they attend networking events to get more information. It turned out that 40.9% of participants attend networking events once a year, 36.4% of participants attend networking events weekly, and 13.6% of participants attend networking events once a month. The main goals of participation are almost the same. Building partnerships, learning business strategy, meeting investors show a 27.3% result, while finding new clients shows a slightly lower 18.2%.

Do you prefer online networking or in person networking?

Also, when asked whether online or offline networking events are more convenient, 68.2% of participants said that both are important. 18.2% said that in-person networking is more convenient, while 13.6% of participants said that online networking is more convenient. From this, we can see that both online and offline networking have their own benefits.

What networking platforms do you use most often?

Our last question was which platform you use for development. In the picture you can see several platforms, including Instagram, Twitter, Telegram, and LinkedIn. Therefore, the participants found Instagram and LinkedIn to be the most suitable. They made up almost the same indicator, that is, 40.4% and 38.5%. As can be seen from the results, Instagram and LinkedIn are convenient platforms for new business starters and create a number of opportunities

How to network effectively as a beginner in business

Networking is very important for anyone starting a business or career. New business owners may face some difficulties in establishing contacts, but one of the main keys to success is networking, and networking is one of the most important and valuable skills. Through networking, you can get various opportunities, advice and of course, various support to develop your business. Networking is about building real relationships (Employment, 2022) [8]. In addition to creating various opportunities for business development, networking also serves to create partners, customers and even jobs. Nowadays, one of the most effective ways to strengthen networking and start a new business is to use social networks. Currently, platforms such as LinkedIn and Instagram are helping people to promote their products and increase business efficiency. Networking is a long-term strategy for forming real relationships, it should not be one-sided, and it can take a long time to build a strong network (Losey, 2023) [9].

Increasing reach via social media: LinkedIn and Instagram

Using social media serves to create opportunities and increase efficiency for any brand. Platforms such as LinkedIn and Instagram are currently considered powerful tools for developing networking. LinkedIn is a great and effective platform for connecting with various businesses, customers, and partners, and through this platform, you can perform tasks such as building trust, gaining a target audience, showcasing your personal business, and saving costs. LinkedIn is also considered a business platform, and currently the number of users is more than 1 billion (Ruby, 2023) [10]. These results show that LinkedIn embodies opportunities that are not available on other platforms. This platform is also very convenient and effective for reaching a target audience. Those who are just starting a business will have a much greater chance of gaining their audience by using this platform to attract people who are interested in their product or service. In conclusion, LinkedIn is the key to success and a valuable tool for new business starters. As we mentioned above, this platform offers many opportunities, makes it easier to work, and speeds up the ability to acquire your own customers. Another advantage of LinkedIn is that it helps to conduct effective business without costs and also serves to expand the team. LinkedIn is a great platform that serves to achieve success and offers the resources you need on this path. Another powerful and effective platform for new business starters is Instagram. Instagram currently has more than 2 billion users worldwide and, according to statistics for 2024, it ranks 3rd in the world in the list of most used social networks (Dean, 2024) [11]. Instagram is very convenient for showcasing a product or service, promoting a brand to the public, and gaining an audience, like LinkedIn. Instagram creates several opportunities for those who start a new business. For example, it creates many opportunities to attract customers, gain subscribers, promote the product to the public, advertise, sell online, and so on. Products can be presented to the public through Instagram in the form of videos. If the video is high-quality, creative, and attracts people's attention, and if famous people are used in addition, it creates the opportunity for the product to become famous not only in one country, but also worldwide (Nyembe, 2024) [12]. For example, "Fenty beauty" is a brand of cosmetics that has become famous through Instagram. Another reason for the popularity of this brand is that it was created by the world-famous singer Rihanna. Rihanna's current number of subscribers is 150 million (Badgalriri, 2018) [13]. Also, the number of subscribers of "Fenty beauty", which has not been established for 10 years, is more than 13 million (Fenty Beauty, 2018) [14]. We can say that the reason for this is Rihanna's popularity. As we have said above, quality,

creative and famous people are an effective way for new business starters and create an opportunity to make a brand famous not only in their own country but also around the world. In conclusion, Instagram is very useful for new business starters and has the opportunity to take your business to the top with over 2 billion users. From this, we can see that networking plays a big role in business management and new business development.

Effective communication builds strong relationships

Effective communication is one of the keys and foundations of relationships. Through effective communication, strong relationships can be established anywhere. Two main factors are needed to establish effective communication. Of these, loyalty and trust. Where there is loyalty, there is trust, and where there is trust, there is loyalty. These two factors are interdependent, and the loss of one of them can instantly destroy long-term relationships and partnerships (Richards, 2019) [15]. Effective relationships are a very necessary factor for business development, especially for those who are just starting a business. Effective relationships create factors such as trust, help, and support between people. According to psychologists, if a person tells someone about his thoughts and feelings, he has taken the first step towards relief and solving the problem (Sutton, 2022) [16]. From this, we can see that effective communication is very important not only in business but also for human life.

There are several factors that go into creating effective communication. Problem solving, listening, and making the right decisions are some of the key factors in effectiveness. Through these factors, you can achieve success, build strong relationships in life and business, and achieve personal and business benefits quickly and easily.

Problem Solving: Problem solving is one of the main aspects of effective communication, and identifying and effectively solving a problem when it arises builds trust, demonstrates mutual respect, and helps build strong relationships. Problem solving also contributes to increasing team motivation and building good relationships with partners. In conclusion, solving problems correctly in business creates strong relationships and serves to achieve success.

Listening: Listening is the most important part of communication. Listening is one of the main keys to achieving success, through which you can achieve a number of results in life and in business. By listening, you can build strong and trusting relationships with new partners and the team. Listening helps to increase mutual trust and respect, make the right decisions. It is also necessary for those who start a new business because active listening helps to master new ideas, facilitate working with a team, and strengthen relationships with customers.

Making the right decision: Making the right decision in business is considered important in creating effective relationships, and by making the right decision, you can establish trusting relationships with partners and customers. Making the right decision ensures the success of a company or enterprise. It is also very important for those starting a new business to study competitors, analyze them, and identify new opportunities. Making the right decision is important in this, and through this, the company can gain its place in the market. According to experts, every decision in business shapes the future of the business. From this, we can see that making the right decision serves to make a new business successful.

Participate in networking events both online and offline

Networking events are considered a great way to do business, as they provide several advantages, such as meeting new people, analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of different businesses, and exchanging ideas. New business starters learn the knowledge they need through these events, exchange ideas with people with a lot of experience, and have the opportunity to increase their chances of success (LinkedIn, 2024) [17].

Why are networking events important?

As we mentioned above, these events help new business starters develop their businesses and through these events they have the opportunity to find investors, customers, and partners for their company. Through these events, new business starters also have the opportunity to get valuable advice from people who are active in their fields (Metral, 2023) [18]. There are several advantages to both networking events. Through offline events, there is an opportunity to solve any problems or give advice face to face. Online events are also developing now. There is an opportunity to conduct webinars through applications such as Telegram, Facebook, Zoom. Regardless of whether it is an online or offline event, webinars serve to achieve success and create new opportunities (Jain, 2024) [19].

Using social media to develop business brand

Social media plays an important role in increasing a business brand. Currently, people spend almost 2 and a half hours a day on social media (Shewale, 2024) [20]. According to data, one of the platforms where people spend the most time is Instagram, with users spending an average of 53 minutes a day on it. (Jain, 2024) [21]. This data shows that social media plays one of the main roles in increasing a business brand. Using social media creates several advantages for those who are just starting a business. By using social media correctly, you can gain an audience, connect with customers, implement partnerships, advertise, sell online, and many other opportunities. Also, if we look at how top brands that are well-known and famous use social media, we can determine that they are active on almost all types of social networks. For example, Nike company. The world-famous Nike company has been actively using various platforms. They currently have 303 million followers on Instagram, almost 350 million on Facebook, and 130 million on Twitter (Times, 2024) [22]. Chanel is also an active user of social media. Although their Instagram following is smaller than Nike's, they are one of the top brands in the world. Chanel currently has over 60 million followers on Instagram. They have over 23 million followers on Facebook and over 13 million followers on Twitter (Panigrahi, 2023) [23]. In short, using social media helps build a brand, gain popularity, gain customer loyalty, and help businesses succeed.

Discussion

Networks are important in expanding businesses, especially for people who are starting out in business. Social media sites such as LinkedIn and Instagram have simplified networking quite a lot and made it more effective. LinkedIn helps businesspeople reach other businesses, customers and clients and this goes a long way in cementing confidence. LinkedIn is an avenue for more than a billion potential clients about what business model to adopt. By joining discussions on LinkedIn group, the entrepreneurs can have great ideas and advices in the sector, which can enable them to

make the best decisions and grow their businesses. Instagram is a very powerful tool since it is a visual driven platform that allows new firms to showcase their goods or services in a more appealing way. The extensive users on the platform indeed enables businesses to have global representation especially where fashion and beauty is concerned. Further, Instagram also come with video posts, stories or even influencer sponsorships that can enhance the public awareness and appreciation of the brand. The example of services offered by the Rihanna “Fenty Beauty” brand indicate that Instagram can be used to create ready market for the brand through millions of potential customers. Customers, partners, and other relevant parties need to be communicated to by the business and its management in order to maintain good relations. People’s trust and loyalty, which are the basic components of long-term business success, are built by active listening, quick resolution of issues, and informed decision-making. Whether in personal or in business relationships, communication as we all know, is a fundamental key. Another good opportunity for the starters to increase their connections are the online and offline network events. Such events make it possible for businessmen to talk to other businessmen who have been in business for a longer period of time and use their experience to get other businessmen or clients. Webinars and other online networking events are a good alternative and expansion opportunity as well.

Conclusion

It's a known fact that networking is vital to anyone who wants to start a business. Using this method, an entrepreneur can meet people, look for partners or clients and extend the scope of their activities. You can use social media such as LinkedIn and Instagram to advance a business. Good communication encourages trust and loyalty which makes relationships strong and healthy. In addition, attending networking events in cyberspace and in your locality helps business owners to benefit from other people's expertise, share ideas and create new ventures. If networking techniques are applied properly and social media is used effectively, new enterprises can enhance their chances of success and survival in the international business arena.

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